

Paper 18

**KOLB’S EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING STRATEGY-AN INNOVATIVE
PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH TO ENHANCE TEACHER
COMPETENCIES OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS**

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ABSTRACT

Teachers play a significant role in providing experiences to the learner, thus act as facilitator. In-depth knowledge of planning and implementing meaningful experience and thereby enhancing students’ knowledge is one of the greatest tasks of teachers. Therefore, teachers must be mindful of different experiential learning strategies to provide hands on experience and to create meaningful learning environment. Since teacher education programme facilitate the early growth and development of Pre-service Teachers, it is essential to provide experience-based education to Pre-service Teachers. Therefore, in the present study an attempt was made to examine the effect of Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers. The study employed 2x3 factorial design. The randomly selected 60 Pre-service teachers of Secondary School level were the samples of the study. Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers were measured using a rating scale prepared by the investigator based on Ten major Teacher Competencies suggested by NCTE. The results of the study revealed that Kolb’s Experiential learning Strategy is significantly effective in enhancing Teaching Competencies of Pre-service Teachers.

Keywords: Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy, Teacher Competencies, Teaching Aptitude, Pre-service Teachers

Introduction

Present-day society needs vibrant teachers who are well qualified and well prepared with academic and professional competencies of the high standard to carry the earnest obligation of

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improving students' learning and attainment and to make them gradually independent and self-actualizing person. The quality and extent of learner achievement are determined mostly by teacher competencies, skills, and motivation. Effective teaching is a very complex task. Over a period with intense training and practices, teachers must be constantly improving and developing their effective teaching skills. Teacher education programme plays a vital role in preparing teachers for classroom processes with theoretical knowledge and practical skills. It is the professional preparation of teachers to enter the noble field of teaching and thereby develops their ability and proficiency that would facilitate and empower them to meet the requirements of the profession and face the challenges.

For the professional development of the teachers, it is essential to engage students with new and innovative ideas about education and try out new classroom activities. Experiential Learning focuses on the experience of teachers developing their classroom practice. Therefore, to improve the quality of Pre-service Teacher's student teachers must be provided with various kinds of experiential activities that would help them to develop new skills, new attitudes, or new ways of thinking. By applying knowledge to experiences they participate in process of learning by doing. In an experiential learning student teacher manage their own leaning by reflecting on their experiences in new and challenging situation. It provides opportunities to learn in real world setting outside the classroom. Such experiences not only enhance subject matter knowledge but also have positive impact on teaching competencies too.

Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory

David Kolb an American Psychologist proposed Experiential Learning Theory. Based on earlier work David Kolb provides a comprehensive theory which lays foundation for education and leaning as lifelong process. According to Kolb (1984) people learn from their experiences and the results of that learning can be reliably assessed and certified for college credit. Internships, field assignment, work or study assignment, structured exercises and role plays, and gaming, simulations and other form of experienced based educations are playing a larger role in the curricula of under graduate and professional programs. Experienced base education has become widely accepted as a method of instruction in colleges and universities across the nation.

Kolb's four-stage model of learning is regarded as classical and as a foundation for experiential learning. It has been widely used in management consultation, leadership training and in research

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in cognitive process skills. Kolb’s four stages Experiential Learning Model describe the cycle of learning in which experience is interpreted through reflection into concept which in turn used a guide for Active Experimentation. The four stages of Kolb’s Experiential Learning Cycle are Concrete Experience, Reflective Observation, Abstract Conceptualization and Active Experimentation. The Details of the Kolb’s Experiential Cycle is Given in Figure1

Figure 1 Kolb’s Experiential Learning Cycle

Rationale for the Study

Experiential Learning is a holistic perspective of learning that combines experience, perception, cognition and behaviour. (Kolb, 2015) It is a process of learning where transformation of experiences leads to the creation of knowledge. Several studies have been conducted by different researchers on experiential learning with regard to different variables. Experimental, qualitative and descriptive studies revealed the significance of experiential learning theories and highlighted the uses of different models of experiential learning. Kolb’s four stage Experiential Learning model has been widely used and actively tested by different researchers in different educational programmes to transform experiences into creating new knowledge and meaningful learning. It has been used extensively in higher education to foster meaningful learning. Even though model has been accepted and used at pre-service teacher education level, very few studies have reported so far. While reviewing the literature the researcher noticed the wide scope of experiential

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learning that could be used effectively at pre-service education. A great deal of previous research conducted at pre-service teacher education level especially in science related subjects (Alkan, 2016) and (Handan, 2017) proved that pre-service teachers enhanced their achievement in subjects such as Biology and Chemistry respectively. (Assab & Awad, 2015) revealed that Experiential learning strategies has positive effect in enhancing performance of EFL teacher’s cognitive skills and motivation for learning. Kolb’s Experiential learning Strategy also helped the pre-service teachers to deliver better constructivist lesson (Kablan & Kaya, 2014). The study conducted by Saalh (2014) revealed that the Combining Video lectures and Kolb’s Experiential Learning has a positive effect on enhancing Pre-service Teacher’s Teaching Competencies. All these studies have proved that Kolb’s Experiential Learning strategy has positive impact on the performance of pre-service teachers. Studies on Kolb’s Experiential Learning also enhanced the achievement of students of secondary school students. (Cheriyana, 2010) study revealed that interest and achievement of secondary school students in mathematics was significantly increased after treatment. (Albright, 2011) also indicated that interest of students towards mathematics was increased significantly. All these studies indicated significant effect of the Experiential Learning Strategies on different secondary school subjects.

Based on the literature reviewed, it has been found that Teacher Competencies are extremely important for teachers. But these are rather unexplored area of research studies with regard to Kolb’s Experiential Learning at Pre-service Teacher Education. Thus descriptive, qualitative and quantitative approaches pertinent to Teacher competencies of Pre-service Teachers is the need of the hour. Thus, the present study is designed to investigate the effect of Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy on Teacher Competencies.

Operational Definitions of the Study

Training Strategies

❖ Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy

Kolb’s Experiential Model is one of the efficient pedagogical models of learning. Kolb proposed that optimal learning takes place when the learner pass through four stage cycle. Concrete Experiences, Reflective Observation, Abstract Conceptualization and Active Experimentation. In the present study Kolb’s Experiential Learning strategy refers to the four-stage cycle model proposed by David A. Kolb through which Pre-service Teachers are trained to implement various

experiential learning strategies in their teaching process.

❖ Conventional Training Strategy

In the present study the Pre-service Teachers of Conventional Training Strategy group were trained using the transactional mode suggested by NCTE (2014) in the area of ‘Curriculum and Pedagogic Studies’ and ‘Pedagogy of Teaching Social Science’ was selected for the study.

Teaching Aptitude

Teaching Aptitude is very essential component for effective teachers. It is an essential prerequisite to achieve success in the field of teaching. Thus, in the present study it is very important to control the effect of Teaching Aptitude. Hence it was selected as Secondary Independent Variable of the study. It is a measure of control by which the effect of the Teaching Strategies on Pre-service Teachers was studied with different levels of Teaching Aptitude. Hence in the present study the investigator used 2x3 Factorial design and tried to control the extraneous variable Teaching Aptitude.

Teacher Competencies

A competence is best described as ‘a complex combination of knowledge, skills, understanding, values, attitudes and desire which lead to effective, embodied human action in the world, in a particular domain’ (Deakin Crick, 2008)

In the present study Teacher Competencies refers to the ability of a Pre-service Teacher to perform multiple complex tasks with more ease and precision. It is measured by ‘Rating Scale on Teacher Competencies’ constructed by the investigator based on Ten major Teacher Competencies suggested by NCTE. The scale is modified by the investigator as per the requirements of Pre-service Teachers. The competencies are: Contextual Competency, Conceptual Competency, Content Related Competency, Transactional Competency, Educational Activities related Competency, Competencies to Develop Teaching Learning Material, Evaluation Competencies, Management Competencies, and Competencies related to working with the Parent, Competencies related to Working with the Community.

Pre-service Teachers

Pre-service Teachers at Secondary School Level are the teacher trainees who undergo training in B.Ed. colleges affiliated to respective universities as per the guidelines laid by NCTE. In the

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present study Pre-service Teachers refers to Pre-service Teachers of Secondary School levels pursuing two-year B.Ed. degree course under Mangalore University of the Academic year 2015-2017.

Methodology

The study is experimental study with 2x3 factorial design. All the pre-service teachers of Dakshina Kannada district were the population of the study. Randomly selected 60 Pre-service Teachers were included as sample of the study. Teacher Competencies of Pre-service teachers were measured using rating scale prepared by the investigator based on Ten Major Teacher Competencies suggested by NCTE. Data was analysed using inferential statistic ANOVA and hypotheses were tested using 0.05 level of significance.

Statement of the Problem: To study the effect of Training Strategies (Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy and Conventional Method) and levels of Teaching Aptitude on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers.

Objective of the Study

Objective One: To study the effect of Training Strategies and Levels of Teaching Aptitude and their interaction effect on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers after partialling out the effect of Pre-achievement.

Hypotheses of the Study

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the effect of Training Strategies and Levels of Teaching Aptitude and their interaction effect on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers after partialling out the effect of Pre-achievement.

Ho_{1.1}: There is no significant difference in the effect of Training Strategies on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers after partialling out the effect of Pre-achievement.

Ho_{1.2}: There is no significant difference in the effect of Levels of Teaching Aptitude on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers after partialling out the effect of Pre-achievement.

Ho_{1.3}: Interaction of Training Strategies and Levels of Teaching Aptitude has no significant effect on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers after partialling out the effect of Pre-achievement.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Objective One: To study the effect of Training Strategies and Levels of Teaching Aptitude and their interaction effect on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers after partialling out the

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effect of Pre-achievement

Summary of 2x3 Factorial Design ANCOVA for Teacher Competencies by taking Pre-achievement as Covariate.

Table 1

Summary of 2x3 Factorial Design ANCOVA scores for Teacher Competencies by taking Pre-achievement as Covariate

	S.S	df	MS	F	P	Result
Teaching Strategy A	495.18	1	495.18	8.35	0.0056	Significant at 0.05 level of significance
Levels of Teaching Aptitude B	127.92	2	63.96	1.08	0.347	Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance
AXB	196.25	2	98.13	1.65	0.2018	Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance
Adjusted error	3142.54	53	59.29			

From the Table 1 it is observed that the ‘F’ ratio for Training Strategies is 8.35 which is greater than the theoretical value 4.08 for degrees of freedom 1 and 53. It indicates that there is a significant difference in the development of Teacher Competencies among Pre-service Teachers trained in different Training Strategies.

The ‘F’ value for Levels of Teaching Aptitude is 1.08 which is lesser than the theoretical value of 3.23 for degrees of freedom 2 and 53. It indicates that there is no significant difference in development of Teacher Competencies among Pre-service Teachers with different levels of Teaching Aptitude.

The ‘F’ value for interaction effect is 1.65 which is lower than the theoretical value 3.23 for degrees of freedom 2 and 53. So it is evident that there is no significant difference in development of Teacher Competencies because of interaction between Levels of Teaching Aptitude and Training Strategies.

To determine which Training Strategy is more effective in developing Teacher Competencies among Pre-service Teachers, the adjusted means of the Training Strategies were calculated. The details are given in the Table 2

Table 2

Adjusted Mean and SD of Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers with respect to Training Strategies

Training Strategies	Adjusted Mean	SD
Kolb’s Experiential Strategy	96.16	2.50
Conventional Training	90.17	3.58

From the Table 2 it is observed that the adjusted mean of Teacher Competencies of Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy is higher than the adjusted mean of Conventional Training Strategy. Hence it is evident that Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy is significantly effective than Conventional Training Strategy in developing Teacher Competencies among Pre-service Teachers.

To visualize the interaction effect of Training Strategies and the Levels of Teaching Aptitude, graphical representation of the mean scores of the Pre-service Teachers with Average, Above Average and Below Average Teaching Aptitude with respect to the development of Teacher Competencies is given in Table 3

Table 3

Mean Scores of Teacher Competencies

Levels of Teaching Aptitude	Training Strategies	
	Kolb’s Experiential Learning	Conventional Training
	Mean Scores	Mean Scores
Low Aptitude	96.87	90.83
Average Aptitude	96.57	90.61
High Aptitude	99.87	81.33

Figure 1 Interaction of Training Strategies and levels of Teaching Aptitude on Teacher Competencies of Pre-service Teachers.

From the Figure1 it is evident that there is no interaction effect of Training Strategies and Levels of Teaching Aptitude on Development of Teacher Competencies among Pre-service Teachers. Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy is more effective than Conventional Training Strategy irrespective of levels of Teaching Aptitude.

Major Findings of the Study

1. Two Training Strategies –Kolb’s Experiential Strategy and Conventional Training Strategy differed in their effects on Teacher Competency of Pre-service Teachers
2. Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy is significantly more effective than the Conventional Training Strategy with respect to Teacher Competency of Pre-service Teachers after partialling out the effect of Pre-achievement
3. Levels of Teaching Aptitude of Pre-service Teachers have no significant effect on Teacher Competency of Pre-service Teachers

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4. Interaction of Training Strategies and Levels of Teaching Aptitude has no significant effect on the development of Teacher Competency among Pre-service Teachers.

Educational Implications

In the present study irrespective of levels of Teaching Aptitude, Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy proved to be effective in developing teacher competencies of Pre-service Teachers. Therefore, Kolb’s Experiential Learning Model and Strategies need to be included in Pre-service Teacher Education Curriculum. Along with theoretical knowledge student teachers need to be trained in the practical usage of this model.

In the present study continuous guidance, suggestions and feedback provided by the investigator, mentor teachers, teacher educators and supervisors benefitted the Pre-service Teachers to develop their Teacher Competencies. Therefore, Pre-service Teacher’s observation schedule on micro teaching and macro teaching need to be strengthened using Kolb’s Learning Strategy developed in the study.

Necessary training and input should be given to teacher educators, supervisors and mentor teachers to provide constructive suggestions and feedback to Pre-service Teachers based on Kolb’s Experiential Learning Strategy.

Various educational organizations such as NCTE, NCERT and UGC along with Teacher Education Institutions should make an effort to train teacher educators and Pre-service Teachers in experiential learning process. Faculty improvement programmes such as refresher courses, orientation courses, workshop, seminars, and symposium to could be organized to impart knowledge and skills of Experiential Learning Strategies

Conclusion

The Kolb’s cycle of learning has been widely used and adapted in the design and conduct of countless educational programmes. Today in higher education, traditional experiential methods are receiving renewed interest and attention, owing in large measure to the changing educational environment. The theory has a vast range of application, including helping students realise themselves, helping teachers become reflexive teachers, identifying learning styles of students, and development of key teacher’s skills. The advantages of Kolb’s theory can be used to provide

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ready directions for application; it gives guidelines for the necessary range of education methods, provides effective connection between theory and practice and offers a theoretical argument for the need and application of experiential activities to improve the practices of teachers.

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